

Sentiment Analysis Tasks and Approaches

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Abstract

Sentiment analysis (SA) or opinion mining extracts and analyses subjective information from various sources such as the web, social media, and other sources to determine people's opinions using natural language processing (NLP), computational linguistics, and text analysis. This analyzed information gives the public's feelings or attitudes about specific items, persons, or ideas and identifies the information's contextual polarity. This systematic review gives a clear image of recent work in sentiment analysis SA; it studies the papers published in the SA field between 2016 and 2020 using the science direct and Springer databases. Furthermore, it explains the various approaches employed and the various uses of SA systems. In science Direct, 99 publications meet our research requirements, whereas, in Springer, 57 papers meet the same conditions, with a total of 156 papers reviewed and assessed in this systematic review. Techniques, performance, language, and the domain have been analyzed.

Keywords

Sentiment analysis; opinion mining; Natural Language Processing; Machine Learning; Deep Learning; word embedding.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sentiment analysis or opinion mining is a computational field that studies people's opinions, sentiments, emotions, ratings, and attitudes towards objects such as products, services, organizations, persons, events, topics, and attributes [1]. Generally, text information can be classified into two main types: facts and opinions. Facts are objective expressions about something. Opinions are usually subjective expressions that describe people's sentiments, speculations, and feelings toward a subject or topic.

Currently, sentiment analysis has many practical applications due to the rapid growth rate of information over the internet; many texts express opinions on review sites, forums, blogs, and social media. Opinions are the basis of almost all human activities and stimulate our behaviors. We have recently noticed that opinionated postings on social media have helped businesses reshape and control public sentiments and emotions, profoundly impacting our political and social organizations. Finding and controlling opinion sites on the web and filtering the information contained in them remains challenging because of the propagation of different sites. Each site typically contains a large volume of opinion text that is not easily decoded in long blogs and forum postings. Therefore, the regular reader will find it difficult to identify relevant sites and get and summarize the opinions involved, so the need for automated sentiment analysis systems arises. Current researches have created different techniques for different tasks of SA, using either supervised or unsupervised methods. Early articles used all types of supervised machine learning techniques (such as Support Vector Machines (SVM), Maximum Entropy (MaxEnt), and Naïve Bayes (NB) and Unsupervised techniques include various sentiment lexicons, syntactic patterns, and grammatical analysis [1][2].

The interest in neural networks was feeble till the late 1990s as they only considered practical with one- or two-layers networks "shallow." Training a neural network with more layers "deep" is computationally very expensive and complicated. Deep Learning (DL) approaches emerged in the last few years as solid computational models capable of autonomously revealing incredibly complex semantic representations of texts from data without any

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feature engineering. These DL techniques are now used in many application fields, as computer vision, speech recognition, and NLP applications such as sentiment analysis tasks[2, 3].

The sentiment analysis system has been classified on a data-level basis into three distinct levels: document, sentence, and aspect. Document-level sentiment analysis (DLSA) classifies the whole opinionated document. A single information unit is represented by a document that provides ideas or thoughts about a particular subject. Sentence level Sentiment analysis (SLSA) classifies each sentence in a document. A sentence is first classified as opinionated or non-opinionated in a process known as subjectivity categorization. After that, the resultant opinionated phrases are labeled as expressing either positive or negative opinions.

Aspect level sentiment analysis, also referred to as aspect-based sentiment analysis (ABSA), is a more fine-grained method than DLSA and SLSA. It extracts and aggregates public perceptions about entities and their associated aspects/features, referred to as targets. With aspect-based sentiment analysis, businesses may pick up on the details of specific traits, components, or entities, identifying what customers like and hate. For instance, "The meal was delicious, but the service was bad," as stated in a restaurant review. In this statement, we have two things, "meal" and "service," each with two matching characteristics, "delicious " and "bad." The process of aspect sentiment classification is to classify the sentiment on the food as positive and on the service as negative. Relating the target with its surrounding context words is hard, making ABSA a challenging task; different context words affect the sentiment polarity towards the target. So capturing semantic connections between the target word and context is a must in building learning models [4].

The contribution of this survey is to provide categorization of a large number of recent articles according to the algorithm used, which can help the researchers in choosing the appropriate one for a particular application and give them the ability to investigate tasks and the evaluation of resources built and used in this field. Then, the accessible benchmark data sets are classified by domain. Performance results are also mentioned for each article to help compare the improvement in performance according to different algorithms used.

The remainder of the research paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides the methodology for the review, which includes subsections on research criteria and data extraction. Section 3 browsed the results; it is divided into five different subsections; the first subsection covers the various languages utilized, then the various functions performed by SA systems are browsed in the second subsection such as general-purpose SA, SA for emotion detection, and SA for judging the improvement in feature selection. Also, different Sentiment Classification (SC) approaches used throughout our study are briefly discussed in the third subsection, then datasets and data domains are presented in the fourth subsection. The final subsection examined performance metrics in the studied research papers. Finally, the article is concluded, and Section 4 discusses future research directions.

METHODOLOGY

A. *Research Criteria*

This Systematic Review aims to identify various studies using sentiment analysis systems based on different classification techniques, and it focuses on the following:

The different techniques in SC.

The Categorizations of different SA systems according to the language studied

The task or scope of the studied SA systems.

The data domains are used for the development of SA systems.

The performance evaluation of different SA systems.

Science Direct database (Elsevier) (<https://www.sciencedirect.com>) and Springer database (<https://www.springer.com>) were searched. The following search keywords were used: "sentiment analysis," "machine learning," and "Deep Learning." The published articles from 2016 to July 2020 were analyzed. However, some relevant studies may have been dropped unintentionally.

Not all linked publications were examined; instead, only those that met the following inclusion criteria were considered:

The research articles based on the previously mentioned keywords only included; the surveys, reviews, and empirical studies are excluded.

(3) The research articles that mainly used text data sets, audio or video, were not included.

(4) All research articles must be fully complete (abstracts only or posters are excluded).

(5) Work published in the period 2016 to July 2020.

Figure 1 depicts the number of papers published in the "Science Direct" and "Springer" databases between 2016 and July 2020 that meet our study requirements. Thus, the SA subject is still a popular study area, as seen by the linear increase in published articles that meet our requirements, even in 2020 with COVID-19 circumstances that impede the publication of new research, indicating that the research in that field is still expanding.

Figure 1. : Publications in sentiment analysis that met our study criteria between 2016 and July 2020 in (a) Science Direct (orange), Springer (blue)

B. Data Extraction

The number of retrieved papers was 114 and 73 articles from Science Direct and Springer, respectively, then papers that do not match the inclusion criteria have been removed. So, only 99, 57 papers from Science Direct and Springer respectively have been included, with 156 from 187. Table A in the appendix shows samples of studied articles in Science Direct and Springer. The first column mentioned the reference number. The language used for the SA application is stated in column two. The classification algorithm used is stated in column three. The purpose of SA is stated in column four.

II. RESULTS

This section details the results obtained from the collected data and their analysis.

A. Language

Figure 2 illustrates the various languages involved in the articles examined in both databases. The most often used language for sentiment analysis systems is English. Around 70% of researched publications either in SD or SP are English. Chinese and Arabic follow English, but with a gap, Arabic and Chinese SA account for around 10% of all articles examined. Chinese research has been overgrown in the previous two years; this might be attributed to the widespread use of the Chinese language on the web due to China's considerable trade with the rest of the world and its enormous population. Examples of Chinese ABSA are browsed through [5], [6], and ABSA with the attention-based mechanism in [7]. Chinese SA in stock market prediction is studied in [8]. Ref[9] concerns are collecting sentiment information for Chinese SA using DL. Ref [10] studies Sentiment Word Co-occurrence and knowledge pair feature extraction in Chinese SA. Arabic SA research is also promising but is limited due to few resources and Lexicons and Arabic's complicated morphology. However, the Arabic language is one of the most popular internet users, resulting in a growing interest in the research area of Arabic SA and resources.[11], [12] The analysis of Arabic SA in various dialects, as well as the enhancement of Arabic ABSA, is addressed in [13], [14]. Developing extensive and comprehensive Arabic lexicons is critical for the advancement of the discipline, articles [15], [16], and [17] focused on building Arabic Lexicons. The importance of FS in Arabic SA is also studied in [18], [19]. SA in other different languages is limited. Figure 3 illustrates the annual number of papers produced in each language.

Fig. 2: Languages in SA articles referenced in this study

Fig. 3 number of articles on Different languages per year a) in SD b) in SP

B. Different views in Sentiment Analysis:

There are two different interpretations of the article's goal as follows:

- It either concentrates on technical aspects of SA models, such as the process of developing SA models via the use of various classification approaches, as in [20], [11], [66], [21], [22], [23], [24], [25] and [26]; In SA, the effect of utilising various feature selection (FS) approaches was investigated [27], [28], [29], [30], [18], [19], and [31]. Building Resources (BRs) like lexicons, dictionaries, and databases are employed as primary resources in SA systems, particularly in languages with few resources such as Arabic [15], [16], [17] and in Urdu Language [32]. Many publications investigate the impact of word/document representation in SA using various embedding approaches as [33], [34], [35], [36], [37], [38], [39], and [18]. Domain adaptation problem is investigated in [36], [40], [41].

OR, different commercial and social applications of SA systems are studied through these articles as stock market prediction in [42], [43], [44], [8], ABSA of products in [45], [46], [13], [14], [6], [47], [48], [49], [31], Opinion summarization in [50], [51]. Ref [52] shows Sarcasm detection model using SA. Cyberbullying and hate speeches detected using SA in [53], and many other applications.

C. Sentiment Classification Approaches:

The primary step in sentiment analysis is to classify the polarity of a given text at the document, sentence, or feature/aspect level as positive, negative, or neutral. Also, sentiment classification is used to determine emotional states such as "angry," "sad," and "happy." The approaches employed in an SC model may be divided into three broad categories: machine learning (ML), lexicon-based (LB), and a hybrid model combining ML and LB. Figure 4

shows the statistics of SC approaches in studied articles in both databases.

Fig. 4 statistics of SC approaches in studied articles

The few paragraphs below give a brief description of the categorization of SC techniques.

1. Machine Learning (ML) can be further subdivided into Supervised Machine Learning SML, Unsupervised Machine Learning UML.

Supervised Machine Learning SML The dataset is divided into a training set and a testing set. The classifier learns from the training data and builds a model that is later used in the classification task of the testing set. This approach generally achieves higher accuracy than that of the unsupervised approach for sentiment analysis. However, it requires building a large corpus (dataset) and labeling it manually by human experts.

Unsupervised machine learning UML extracts patterns from a dataset without using known or labeled outcomes as a guide. Therefore, unlike supervised machine learning, unsupervised machine learning approaches cannot be immediately applied to a regression or classification issue because the output data values are unknown. UML has been divided into clustering and association; the most common example of unsupervised machine learning algorithms are K-Means and Apriori Algorithm.

A mix of SML and UML is a Semi-Supervised Learning SSL. Algorithms that are based on SSL have both labeled and unlabeled data sets. In SSL, an initial classifier can be obtained by including information previously extracted from an existing sentiment lexicon into sentiment classifier model learning, referring to this information as labeled instances and using them directly to limit the model's predictions on unlabeled instances using popularized expectation criteria [54],[55], [56]. Both SML and UML are categorized into traditional machine learning TML or deep learning DL.

1.1 Traditional Machine Learning (TML): Several algorithms in this category are either supervised or unsupervised. SML as Support Vector Machine SVM, Bayesian network, Naïve Bayes (NB), decision tree (DT), maximum entropy (MaxEnt), logistic regression, and k nearest neighbor (KNN). From the 157 articles studied here, 82 out of 157 research articles in both databases are based on TML, as shown in figure 4. SVM and NB are the most TML algorithms used, as shown in figure 5.

1.2 Deep learning (DL): A growing field of study involves the encoding of supervised or unsupervised learning features inside a hierarchical structure. DL has presented outstanding contributions in many applications as

computer vision, named-entity recognition, and speech recognition[57]. Since 2016, DL methods have been widely employed in SA. This review consists of 80 out of 157 research articles in both databases based on different DL techniques used either as a primary technique or as a part of a hybrid system. These articles are distributed as shown in figure 4, which clarifies the increasing importance of deep learning. Multi-layers automatic feature representation can be obtained using DL models [58]; [59]. DL is effective in extracting implicit semantic features, which aids in domain transfer. We significantly minimized feature engineering, human involvement, and computation time by incorporating deep learning algorithms into SA tasks. [60]. The most often used DL models are Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), and its variations LSTM, BiLSTM.

2. Lexicon-based approach: The lexicon-based method is usually implemented using unlabelled data to predict the polarity. Because of their simplicity, scalability, and computational efficiency, these methods are mainly used to solve general-purpose SA problems. However, they rely heavily on human work on annotating the data and sometimes experience low coverage. The lexicon-based approach is further divided into dictionary-based and corpus-based. The dictionary-based approach finds opinion seed words and then searches the dictionary of their synonyms and antonyms. The corpus-based approach begins with a seed list of opinion words and then finds other opinion words in a large corpus to help find opinion words with context-specific orientations. From the 157 articles studied here, 19 out of 157 research articles in both databases are based on LB, as shown in figure 4. Articles [61], [62], [39],[82], [63] and [32],are examples of superiority is SA using LB approach.

3. Hybrid approach: Arises from the combination of the lexicon-based approach with machine learning and is proved to enhance the performance of SA systems as in [64], [46], [65], [35],[66],[67], [68]

Fig. 5 SC Techniques used in studied articles (a) SD (b) SP

D. Datasets and Domain

Table B summarizes the most frequently used data sets in conjunction with their related articles. The data can be classified according to the domain as follows:

- 1- Social networking: Facebook, Twitter, microblogs as Sina, a Chinese microblog, Edinburgh corpus (ED), The Stanford Sentiment corpus (STS), Sanders, SemEval2013 task2, SemEval2013, website Donanim Haber, a prominent domain-specific blogs in Turkey and Wikipedia.

- 2- Product Review: Includes data from many products, electronics, apparel, electronics, reviews from the Google Play store, numerous SemEval jobs such as SemEval 2013 and 2014, and SenTube product review.
- 3- Service Review: Hotel reviews in Semeval 2016 Task 5, Restaurants, review from Trip Advisors web site, booking web site, Chinese tourism review, and Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC) review sites.
- 4- Specific data: as Email spam dataset, Arabic Online Commentary (AOC) dataset, Banks comments, Online surveys, SMS Banking survey, COAE natural disease dataset Chinese, data for a language that is not a commonly used one as Urdu Language, PubMed abstracts, and Linguistic data consortium (LDC) parallel data[69].
- 5- Movies review data: IMDB, MR, and RT datasets.
- 6- News: Articles from online news sources, book reviews, periodicals, short stories, and Wikipedia.

Fig. 6: Different Domains of data

- 7- Health: Clinical publications, online healthcare forums, Drugs.com.
- 8- Business: Stock market as (<https://stocktwits.com/>), and financial information as the Bloomberg website.

E. Performance measures:

Performance measures used throughout articles in this review are: precision Pr, recall R, and F –score (F1) are computed as follows:

$$Pr(pos) = \frac{TP}{(TP + FP)}, Pr(neg) = \frac{TN}{(TN + FN)} \quad (1)$$

$$R(pos) = \frac{TP}{(TP + FN)}, R(neg) = \frac{TN}{(TN + FP)} \quad (2)$$

$$F1(pos) = \frac{2 * (P(pos) * R(pos))}{(P(pos) + R(pos))}, F1(neg) = \frac{2 * (P(neg) * R(neg))}{(P(neg) + R(neg))} \quad (3)$$

Where Pr, R, F1, TP, FP, TN, and FN represent Precision, Recall, F1 score, true positives, false positives, true negatives, and false negatives.

The area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC or AUROC) is another essential accuracy measure. It does not rely on the cut-off values of the posterior probabilities. AUC is defined as follows:

$$AUC(positive\ sentiment) = \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \left(\frac{TP}{(TP + FN)} \right) d \left(\frac{FP}{(FP + TN)} \right) = \int_0^1 \left(\frac{TP}{P} \right) d \left(\frac{FP}{N} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$AUC(negative\ sentiment) = \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \left(\frac{TN}{(TN + FP)} \right) d \left(\frac{FN}{(FN + TP)} \right) = \int_0^1 \left(\frac{TN}{N} \right) d \left(\frac{FN}{P} \right) \quad (5)$$

TP: True Positives, FN: False Negatives, FP: False Positives, TN: True Negatives, P: Positives (positive sentiment), N: Negatives (negative sentiment). The values of the AUC range from 0.5 to 1. An AUC of 0.5 means that the model cannot do better than a random selection, while a value of 1 indicates a perfect prediction.

A brief description of the most common algorithms that give the best performance throughout the articles are listed in the following few paragraphs in descending order from the most significant number of papers used to the minor no of papers:

- Support Vector Machine Classifiers (SVM): This supervised machine learning technique tends to determine linear separators in the space, which can best separate the different classes by maximizing marginal hyperplane (MMH), which will minimize the error. Text data are ideally suited for SVM classification because of the sparse nature of the text. However, they tend to be correlated with one another and generally organized into linearly separable categories[70]. SVM can construct a nonlinear decision surface in the original feature space by mapping the data instances non-linearly to an inner product space. Then, the classes can be separated linearly with a hyperplane [71]. Examples for best performance results using SVM: in Ref [72], SA of Italian language achieves Acc of 91.58%, while in Arabic [15] Acc 90%, ABSA Acc of 95.4% in [14], and the use of optimization for FS in addition to SVM for SC enhance the Arabic Acc 95.93% in [19]. Acc of 91.64% in [73] for English using an ensemble of SVM and NB, English SA Acc 91.67% in [74]
- Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs): CNN's are modifications of feed-forward NNs with the following properties: (i) convolutional layers: A CNN usually has one or more convolutional layers that build adjoining locative features (hidden units); (ii) sparse connectivity: instead of having fully connected neurons, inputs of hidden units in the layer l are from a subset of units in layer $l-1$ that have adjoining locative features; (iii) shared weights: Units belonging to the same local features share the same weights (weight vector and bias); and (iv) Pooling: instead of using all the local features at the next level, they have a pooling layer that computes either the average or the minimum or the maximum of these features. For NLP tasks, convolutional layers release local features around a window of a given sequence of words. In addition, they are often gathered to extract higher-level features [75]. 36 out of 157 articles (23%) used CNN in SC. Spanish ABSA obtains an Acc of 70.5 % in[46], SA for Thai children stories achieves F1- score of 81.7% of using CNN in [76], Acc 89.5% in Arabic Algerian Dialect SA using CNN in [16], Chinese SA in [77]gets 92.52% Acc, Short text SA [135]results in Acc 0.92 Micro-AUC 0.98 Macro-AUC0.97
- Long Short-Term Memory LSTM: Artificial Neural Network (ANN) that contains direct cycles in their hidden connections is a recurrent neural network (RNN). RNN can only process a finite number of sequences[78] due to the diminishing gradient; Long short-term memory (LSTM) networks are a variation of RNN with a memory cell that can maintain states over long periods, defeating the long-distance dependencies problem of RNNs [79]. An LSTM is a memory cell, ct , which is recurrently connected to itself. It multiplies using three components: an input gate it , a forget gate ft , and an output gate ot . These gating vectors have a range of $[0, 1]$. The cell makes deliberate choices regarding memory storage and when to access units via open and closed gates. Figure 5 indicates that LSTM and Bidirectional LSTM (BiLSTM) were employed in SC in 40 out of 157 publications (about 25%) in both databases.

- In [33] SA using BiLSTM achieves F1- of 91.3%, also attention-based bi-directional long short-term memory recurrent neural network AttBiLSTM used for Korean text SA [37] with Acc 91.95 to 92.66, F1 of 92.43 to 93. Chinese text BiLSTM -SA gives Acc of 84.36% in [9] using Sina, a Chinese Microblog. In [144], the use of LSTM with attention mechanism for English and Japanese SA achieved Japanese Acc of 87.2 English Acc of 73.7. LSTM is used for Multilanguage SA as [147].
- Naïve Bayes NB: A supervised probabilistic approach that can predict a probability distribution over a set of classes, given an observation of input, rather than only outputting the most likely class to which the observation should belong. Probabilistic classifiers provide a valuable classification as a standalone classifier or combined with other classifiers into ensembles. NB is widely used for text classification. It is based on the Bayes probability theorem in which the posterior probability of class or given predictor is calculated.
The NB algorithm is used in about 31 of 157 (about 20%) in studied articles. For example, [29] achieves Acc 88.0% to 99.89% for different datasets used, while Acc of 0.7, R of 0.35, Pr of 0.47 were obtained in Arabic tweets SA in [63]. In [80] English SA using POS features and MNB classifier gives Acc of 74% Pr of 77% R74% F1-of 74%
- Rule-based Approach RB: In which a set of rules are used to model the data space. The left-hand side shows the feature set expressed in a contrapuntal way, and the right-hand side is the class label. The conditions are based on the term presence; absence is rarely used because it is not informative in sparse data. The most common criteria used in forming rules are support and confidence [81]. Support is the number of all examples in the training data set which are relevant to the rule. Confidence is the conditional probability that the rule's right-hand side is fulfilled if the left-hand side is fulfilled [82]. The RB is used in about 8 of 157 (about 5%) in studied articles. Here RB is the only approach for SC in articles [83], [84]. In most cases, better performance is obtained when used within the ensemble of classifiers or in conjunction with another classifier as RB+LB in [65]. Combining RB with CNN in English ABSA in [85] obtained Pr 79.25%, R 88.45%, F1 83.24%, and Acc of 87% in laptop reviews. [86] ensemble (RB, NB, SVM, and RNTN) achieves an F score of 94.49%
- Ensemble-Based Classifiers: They can be used to obtain better performance than using single learning algorithms. The Homogeneous Ensemble of Neural Networks (HEN) (comprising probabilistic neural networks (PNN) and Back Propagation Neural Networks (BPN)) has shown superior performance in [87] achieving correctness (Pr) 90.3%, completeness 93%, effectiveness 91.5%, efficiency 90.1%. other ensemble classifiers as in [88], [89], [86], [24], [67] are shown exceptional performance.

Figure 5 above shows the top ten algorithms that achieved the best performance results. The SVM algorithm is the predominant one with the greatest number of papers in our study that achieves better performance in different SA applications, followed by different DL algorithms as CNN, LSTM.

III. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This systematic review summarizes recent advances in SA methods and applications. A total of 157 papers were analyzed and summarized. These papers contribute to various disciplines by demonstrating how SA methods may be used to various real-world problems. From a linguistic standpoint, we can infer that English is the most studied language in SA applications. However, due to a shortage of resources, research in other languages continues to

develop. Despite its complexity and scarcity of materials, SA in the Arabic language is gaining the popularity of the vast number of individuals who use Arabic on the internet and social media. SA has rapidly developed in the Chinese language during the last two years. As a result, Chinese and Arabic were the second and third most prevalent SA fields.

Different tasks are investigated, including the basic sentiment analysis tasks SLSA, ABSA, and DLSA, and those other specific tasks rely on the essential tasks to achieve the goal such as stock market prediction, building recommendation system in many data domains, opinion summarization, dialect classification, building resources and to solve domain adaptation problem. Different data set domains are used throughout the studied articles. However, social media sites and different microblogs take a significant portion due to their primary role in expressing opinions or feelings about a specific topic or product. There are different techniques used in the SA task. SVM algorithms are the most prominent TML and achieved the best results in many systems studied through this SR. DL techniques have been growing very fast in the last few years, especially since 2016. There is no need for feature engineering and a remarkable ability to treat vast amounts of data like that on the web and social media. DL algorithms as CNN and LSTM achieved high-rank results in this SR. DL techniques in languages other than English, especially in Arabic, are a promising field. The Arabic language complex features benefit more from DL and still need to be tackled more deeply.

TABLE A SAMPLE OF STUDIED ARTICLES

Ref	Language	Algorithm	Task
Science Direct			
[90]	English	Multilayer ANN	SA of a product review
[91]	English	LSTM, Bi-L STM, C-LSTM, and Tree-LSTMs	SC using cascade architecture
[92]	English	CNN, RNN	Decision-making to choose, design, and manufacture Electric vehicles.
[93]	English	LSTM + attention layer	SA with multiple attention
[88]	English	Ensemble of BiLSTM, attention	Multi-domain SA.
[94]	English	NB, DT, RF, KNN, GRU, CNN, and three-way convolutional recurrent neural network 3CRNN	SC of Drug reviews.
[95]	English	ASP-BRNN	Extracting semantic information, enhancing the SA system
[96]	English	LB+recursive neural tensor network model	SA for reviewing and extracting knowledge from a large body of scientific literature
[97]	English	dilated convolutional neural network (D-CNN)	Extraction of long-term contextual semantic features for SA,
[98]	English	4-layer sequential NN	SA of PubMed abstracts.
[99]	English	the gradient boosting trees	SA of randomly sampled MOOCs and students' to predict MOOC learner satisfaction and estimate their relative effects.
[100]	English	CNN-LSTM	Earn sentiment-specific vectors from CNN and LSTM.
[101]	English	Fuzzy rule-based, LB	SA using fuzzy logic.
[102]	English	LSTM,MLP	aspect-level sentiment classification (HHAS) using hierarchical human-like strategy
[103]	English	target-dependent CNN (TCNN)	target-level SA
[104]	English	RB, SVM, CNN and BiLSTM.	Citation SC in clinical research publications

[105]	English	Dynamic Architecture for Neural Networks (DAN2) and SVM	Create a feature set for Twitter SA that is domain-transferable.
[106]	English	LR	SA of text comments of Bank customers
[107]	English	NB	Improving the accuracy of decision support systems for SA
[108]	English	SVM	
[109]	English	SVM, KNN, subspace discriminant (SSD), Tree	SA for Prediction of venous thromboembolism
[110]	English	CNN	Twitter text SA
[111]	English	(NB + ME)	Performance comparison between Cross-ratio uninorm (NB & ME), LB methods in SA
[112]	English	fuzzy logic+LB	Hybrid sentence level SA
[113]	English	Ensemble LR, NB, LDA, LR, and SVM +soft computing	Build a multiobjective weighted voting ensemble classifier for text SC
[114]	English	Classification And Regression Tree CART, ANN, Support Vector Regression (SVR) and Multiple Linear Regressions (MLR)	
[115]	Chinese	AttBiLSTM	Fine-grained SC for the Chinese language using DL
[77]	Chinese	CNN	Chinese text SA CNN
[13]	Arabic	NB, DT, KNN, SVM	Enhancing ABSA for Arabic reviews
[15]	Arabic	CNN,LSTM,,NB,DT,RF, XGBoost, SVM	Building a huge dataset for Arabic reviews.
[116]	Arabic	<i>Combining CNN and LSTM models.</i>	Arabic SA using ensemble DL
	Arabic	Combining CNN and LSTM models.	Arabic SA using ensemble DL
[39]	Arabic	LB	Expanding an Arabic SL using a word embedding
[117]	Malayalam	NB,SVM,RF	SA of Malayalam Tweets using TML
[118]	Spanish	Tree augmented naive Bayes (TAN)	SA during critical events on two datasets in Spanish using Bayesian networks
[119]	Punjabi	DNN	Punjabi text SA using DL
[120]	English, Chinese	CHL-PRAE (RAE +HowNet lexicon)	combination of RAE, LB for sentence-level SA
[121]	English, Chinese	lexicon integrated two-channel CNN-LSTM	SA using CNN-LSTM and CNN-BiLSTM models with the sentiment lexicon information
Springer			
[122]	English	Ensemble of NB, SVM ,DT	Building a deceptive detection model
[123]	English	LSTM+Attention mechanism	Document SA using CSNN
[124]	English	Deep BiLSTM	Analysis of aspect position information in ABSA
[125]	English	Linear SVC and LR	SC using TF-IDF for FS
[48]	English	CNN	ABSA with ontologies, CNN with stochastic parameter optimization
[126]	English	Deep Feed-Forward NN	A decision in tourism sector projects using SA
[127]	English	Neural network AutoRegressiveNNAR	Inclusion of count predicators in SA for stock prediction
[128]	English	attention + LSTM	stock closing price prediction using SA
[129]	English	recursive auto-encoders	Recursive autoencoder for SA
[130]	English	DT+Genetic Algorithm+Swarm	using two optimization algorithms and DT for SA
[131]	English	DT,RF,LinearRegressionWithSGD, Lasso regression with SGD(LassoWithSGD), (RidgeRegressionWithSGD), SVR	Embedding ontology features as lexical, semantic, and their combination in SA

[132]	English	Fuzzy C-Means	Big Data SC using Fuzzy C-means
[133]	English	NN, MLP	prediction of abnormal stock return by SA
[134]	English	Paragraph Vector	Using Weighting word Scheme in SA
[135]	English	Hierarchical Dirichlet processes (HDP)+ affinity propagation (AP) algorithm	SA for Latent sentiment topic modeling
[136]	Chinese	RNN	Chinese public figures opinion polling
[137]	Chinese	U-SVM(Universum SVM)	Universum SVM –SC for better SA performance
[18]	Arabic	SVM	DL(CNN+LSTM) for FS+use of FastText embedding
[19]	Arabic	SVM	Use of Optimization for FS in Arabic SA
[138]	Thai	SVM+ rules	error analyzes in SA for Thai children stories
[139]	Thai	SVM	SA of Thai children stories
[140]	Bangla	an attention-based CNN	SA with an attention mechanism
[7]	English Chinese	LSTM	The significance degree values for various words in a phrase are determined through the use of an attention-based process in ABSA
[141]	English, Chinese	NB,KNN,LR,RF,DT,SVM, GBDT	feature extraction methodology for SA of product reviews
[142]	English, Hungarian	SVM	SA on social media over various genres and languages
[143]	Turkish and English	NBM,SVM,LR, DT	Query expansion FS in SA

TABLE B: MOST COMMON DATASETS

Dataset	Ref
Review data from Amazon https://www.amazon.com/	[54],[38], [72], [9],[144], [145], [87],[73], [146], [68], [156]
Social media (twitter ,Facebook,instagram) comments on different topics	[21], [147], [148], [149], [20]
IMDB Movie Review, http://www.imdb.com/	[150] , [28, 38] , [89] , [86] , [151] , [147] , [152], [146], [153],[156]
The movies dataset RT: http://www.rottentomatoes.com	[38], [151]
SemEval-2015	[7]
MR- https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/pabo/movie-review-data/	[150], [20], [35], [73], [146]
SST: The Stanford sentiment treebank	[150], [11], [34] ,[38], [121], [146], [154]
Stanford-Sentiment140 corpus of 1,600,000 training tweets	[155], [86], [17], [156], [157]
ASTD: Arabic Sentiment Tweets Dataset	[116] , [158], [18]
SemEval 2013	[34],[86]
SemEval-2014 http://alt.qcri.org/semEval2014/task4	[86], [5], [45], [20], [159], [160],[7], [161]
SemEval-2016	[162], [23], [7], [163], [49], [153], [14], [13]
Tweet dataset collected by Dong et al. [164]	[5], [45], [161]
Chinese datasets cover four domains: car, notebook, camera, and phone.	[5], [20], [7]
Yelp Business at : https://www.yelp.com/dataset	[165], [150], [146], [166]
Real Tweet Dataset: The health care reform (HCR) dataset in 2010.	[55] , [23]
Real Tweet Dataset: Stanford sentiment gold standard (STS-Gold)	[52],[74], [20]
TripAdvisor web site	[148], [72] , [20], [114], [68]

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